

ILSs mapping /D2.2

WP2. ANIPH project baseline, T2.2-Setting the basis for ANIPH effective contribution to ILSs (Information & labelling system(s))

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List of Abbreviations

Acronym	Full Form
ANIPH	Avoiding the Negative Impacts produced by Plastic materials in Humanitarian contexts (EU project)
ASTM	American Society for Testing and Materials
BBpPs	Biobased biodegradable plastics products
CEN	European Committee for Standardization
DoA	Description of Action
DPP	Digital Product Passport
ESPR	Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation
FTC	Federal Trade Commission
GCD	Green Claims Directive
ILS	Information & labelling system(s)
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
MDR	Medical Device Regulation
MSF	Médecins Sans Frontières

OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
PHA	Polyhydroxyalkanoates
PQ	Prequalification
PPWR	Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation
REACH	Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals
SSbD	Safe and Sustainable by Design
UDI	Unique Device Identifier
UNHCR	United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees
VFA	Value for Action
WHO	World Health Organization
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This deliverable provides a systematic mapping of existing Information and Labelling Systems (ILS) relevant to biobased and biodegradable plastic products (BBpPs), with a focus on their application in medical wound care products and packaging for humanitarian contexts. The work forms part of ANIPH Work Package 2, task 2.2 and establishes the foundation to information and labelling system for subsequent activities on Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD), data generation, and policy contribution.

Purpose

The objective was to identify which standards, certifications, tests, and labels currently apply to BBpPs and medical packaging, to assess their coverage of environmental, social, economic, and technical aspects, and to define how ANIPH can contribute to their future development. The mapping provides clarity on existing requirements, highlights inconsistencies, and identifies how and where data should be recovered from. The focus is on the EU.

Key Findings

- Comprehensive technical coverage exists for safety, sterility, and some performance tests through EU Medical Device Regulation (MDR), EN, ISO, and ASTM standards.
- Environmental coverage is relatively strong for controlled biodegradation and compostability, but weak for real-world disposal scenarios such as open burning or unmanaged landfills, which are common in humanitarian settings.
- Socio-economic aspects are underrepresented in current ILS. Procurement frameworks seldom integrate sustainability criteria, cost-performance data for BBpPs is scarce, and existing labels are not always accessible to low-literacy or multilingual user groups.
- Systemic barriers include inconsistent terminology across standards (EN, ISO, ASTM, national), limited transparency in certification schemes, and a lack of alignment between labels and actual waste management infrastructure.

Relevance for ANIPH

For wound care products and packaging in humanitarian operations, these gaps highlight the need for a tailored ILS framework that integrates:

- Technical data on safety, sterility, performance, and traceability (WP4, Preliminary manufacturing of materials for wound dressing and packaging).
- Environmental and end-of-life evidence from realistic field conditions (WP9, End of life: Safe and sustainable biodegradation and recyclability validation).
- Standardisation and policy alignment to ensure credibility and uptake (WP11, ANIPH SSbD assessment and enabling conditions).
- Consumer and professional perspectives to ensure information is clear, trusted, and usable under emergency conditions.

Next Steps

The insights from this mapping will feed directly into later ANIPH deliverables:

- D11.5 (Final ANIPH contributions to ILSs): consolidation of a project-specific ILS framework and contributions to European and international standardisation.
- D12.1 (Final report on policy briefs/recommendations): translation of findings into policy guidance and recommendations for public authorities, procurement bodies, and humanitarian actors.

By identifying both strengths and gaps in current ILSs, this work positions ANIPH to create an integrated, evidence-based, and context-sensitive framework. This will support the safe, sustainable, and socially acceptable adoption of innovative wound care products and packaging in humanitarian settings.

1.Introduction

1.1. Relevance of Information and Labelling Systems (ILS)

Information and labelling systems (ILS) are essential for ensuring that products are used safely and correctly. They provide users with reliable information on product function, risks, and disposal. In medical contexts, labels are directly linked to patient safety and professional practice. They help avoid misuse and ensure compliance with regulatory frameworks such as the EU Medical Device Regulation (EU 2017/745) [1].

For medical wound care products and their packaging, ILS must meet dual demands. On the one hand, packaging must preserve sterility, usability, and traceability. On the other hand, it must respond to sustainability goals such as biodegradability and safe end-of-life management. The European Green Deal and the Circular Economy Action Plan emphasise the importance of avoiding misleading claims on biodegradability, since incorrect disposal can worsen pollution problems [2]. Integrating safety, performance, and environmental information in ILS is therefore necessary.

Humanitarian settings pose additional challenges. Health products are often distributed during emergencies where speed, clarity, and reliability of information are critical. Users may include both trained health workers and non-professionals with limited literacy. The World Health Organization (WHO) stresses that poor communication of instructions in health emergencies undermines effective care and increases risks [3]. In such contexts, packaging labels must provide clear and simple guidance for correct use and disposal.

Waste management infrastructure is often absent in crisis zones. Open dumping or uncontrolled burning of plastic medical waste is common, leading to air pollution, release of toxic substances, and increased infection risks [4]. WHO guidelines highlight that safe waste segregation and disposal are essential even under emergency conditions. For biobased and biodegradable products, ILS must make clear under which conditions materials degrade safely, to avoid misconceptions that could lead to unsafe disposal practices.

For healthcare workers and affected populations, ILS provides trust and reliability in products. In situations of scarcity and stress, labels can serve as a bridge between safe medical care and

sustainable resource management. By integrating safety, usability, and environmental guidance, ILS contributes to both immediate survival and longer-term sustainability goals. This dual role gives ILS societal value in fragile contexts, where clear information can improve health outcomes while reducing negative environmental impacts.

1.2. Goals of ILS in the ANIPH project

The aim of ANIPH is to avoid the negative impacts produced by plastic materials in humanitarian contexts by developing safe and sustainable biobased and biodegradable plastic products (BBpPs). Information and labelling systems (ILS) play a central role in achieving this aim. Within the project, ILS are understood as the interface between product performance, regulatory compliance, sustainability requirements, and end-user understanding.

The goals of ILS in the ANIPH project can be summarised as follows:

1.2.1. Understanding the current system

The first step is to examine the ILS landscape as it exists today. This includes international standards, regulations, certification schemes, and voluntary labelling initiatives relevant for BBpPs in medical and humanitarian contexts. The mapping will allow identification of which technical, environmental, social, and economic aspects are already covered, and to what extent they are supported by verifiable data in this project.

1.2.2. Identifying gaps and inconsistencies

Many existing ILS have been developed for food packaging, consumer goods, or general sustainability certification. Medical and humanitarian uses pose additional demands that may not be fully addressed. The project will analyse where current systems are incomplete, inconsistent, or not adapted to fragile settings. Gaps may include technical issues (e.g. biodegradation conditions), social issues (e.g. accessibility of labels for low-literacy populations), or inconsistencies across standards in different geographies.

1.2.3. Towards a usable and tailored system

The final objective is to define how ANIPH products can be integrated into a usable ILS framework. This framework must ensure safe use and disposal of medical wound care products and their packaging in emergency settings while also communicating sustainability attributes in a credible

way. A tailored approach will consider Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) principles, traceability requirements, and user acceptability.

1.2.4. Recommendations for the field

Beyond the immediate needs of the project, ANIPH aims to provide recommendations for improving ILS in the broader field of biobased and biodegradable medical products. This includes guidance for standardisation bodies, policymakers, and humanitarian organisations on how to harmonise sustainability information with safety and usability requirements. The expected outcome is a set of contributions that improve trust, comparability, and adoption of BBPs across different contexts.

1.3. Scope and Boundaries of the Mapping Exercise

1.3.1. Scope

Types of ILS covered: international standards (e.g. ISO, ASTM), European regulations and directives, certification schemes, voluntary eco-labels, and sector-specific initiatives in packaging and medical devices.

Dimensions covered:

- Environmental (biodegradability, recyclability, life-cycle impact),
- Social (usability, accessibility, acceptability),
- Economic (procurement, market adoption),
- Technical (safety, toxicity, performance).

Target groups:

- Health professionals,
- Humanitarian aid workers and responders
- Social care professionals
- Patients, and affected populations
- Regulatory and procurement bodies

1.3.2. Boundaries

The mapping does not substitute for Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) or risk assessment, though it identifies where such data is needed.

Not product-specific validation: the exercise does not test or certify ANIPH products; it prepares the ground for later work packages (WP4, WP9, WP11) where testing and validation will take place.

Not exhaustive of all labelling domains: focus remains on health-related packaging and humanitarian use.

1.4. Methodology

The mapping exercise is based on desk research using public databases, scientific literature, and policy documents. The work follows six main steps. First, an inventory of existing ILS is compiled, covering international standards (e.g. ISO, ASTM), European frameworks (e.g. EU regulations, EMAS), certification schemes (e.g. OK Compost), and eco-labels (e.g. EU Ecolabel, Blue Angel, Ökotex). Second, an overview of topics in current ILS is created to see which aspects they address, such as environmental issues, social aspects, economic factors, and technical requirements.

Third, an ILS gap analysis identifies missing elements and inconsistencies. Fourth, the exercise focuses on selecting components relevant for ANIPH products, specifying which data points (e.g. biodegradation methods, sterility requirements, traceability codes) are needed for wound care products and their packaging in humanitarian settings.

Fifth, a strategy to obtain missing data from other WPs is developed. For instance, WP4 will generate safety and performance data, WP9 will test products in real contexts, and WP11 will support alignment with policy and standardisation. Finally, the consumer perspective is integrated by reviewing studies and reports on awareness, acceptance, and behaviour. This ensures that ILS design considers the needs of healthcare professionals, humanitarian workers, and affected populations, including those with low literacy or limited resources.

Figure 1. Methodological flow of the ILS mapping exercise.

2. ILS Inventory

2.1. Map of the different information and labelling systems

The mapping of ILS in ANIPH connects two perspectives: the manufacturing cycle of the product and the journey of the user. On the one hand, data is generated during product design, production, and testing (materials, safety, environmental performance, end-of-life pathways). On the other hand, this information must reach healthcare workers, humanitarian responders, and end-users in a way that is clear, trustworthy, and actionable. ILS acts as the bridge between these two perspectives, translating technical data into usable guidance that supports safe use, proper disposal, and sustainable outcomes under real-world conditions.

Figure 2. ILS relations to product, system, and user specifics.

2.2. Standards, Certification, and Substantiating Claims

- Standards: Suppliers, economic operators, or conformity assessment bodies use standards, often harmonized or referenced in regulations to demonstrate that a product meets the necessary regulatory requirements.
- Using Standards (Regulatory Requirement and Supporting Information): Standards remain voluntary unless they are "harmonised" or cited in a regulation. With harmonised

standards, a presumption of conformity applies. Standards demonstrate compliance and support the implementation of legal mandates, as well as substantiating information shared about product features voluntarily as general sector and/or global practice.

- Certification Schemes and labelling: Proving conformity to standards is displayed by getting labels or certificates from accredited bodies. Certification bodies like TÜV Austria and DIN CERTCO are trusted and accredited for carrying out specific tests detailed in standards to issue labels and certificates and demonstrate compliance.
- Substantiating Claims: Claims regarding marketing, environmental, and health performance, whether a regulatory requirement or voluntarily shared, increasingly require backing with scientific data and proof of conformity.

2.2.1. European-level standards and certifications

At the European level, regulatory and standardisation frameworks apply both to medical products and to their packaging. For wound care products in humanitarian contexts, both layers are relevant.

The Medical Device Regulation (MDR 2017/745) sets the baseline for the medical product¹. It requires that labels include safety information, traceability, and instructions for correct use and disposal. It also specifies that information must be comprehensible to both professional and non-professional users, which is particularly relevant in emergency and humanitarian settings. [1]

The new Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation (PPWR), currently under preparation for implementation, will specify technical requirements for compostable packaging. It addresses design requirements, recyclability, and mandatory labelling obligations to align with the principles of a circular economy. The regulation introduces harmonised disposal and material identification labels across the EU, aiming to reduce consumer confusion and improve waste management. [5]

The EU Ecolabel is a voluntary certification scheme that can apply to a wide range of products, including packaging. While it is not specific to medical products, it provides principles for

¹ In the **European Union**, the classification of medical devices is governed by the **Medical Device Regulation (MDR) (EU) 2017/745**, which has been fully applicable since **26 May 2021** (it replaced the old Medical Devices Directive 93/42/EEC and Active Implantable Medical Devices Directive 90/385/EEC). Medical devices are divided into four **risk-based classes**:

1. **Class I** – Low risk; Examples: bandages, non-invasive instruments, spectacles.
2. **Class IIa** – Low-to-medium risk; Examples: hearing aids, infusion pumps, dental fillings, surgical gloves.
3. **Class IIb** – Medium-to-high risk; Examples: ventilators, anesthesia machines, bone fixation plates.
4. **Class III** – Highest risk; Examples: pacemakers, heart valves, implantable defibrillators, breast implants.

transparency and verifiable claims (e.g. biodegradability, recyclability) that may serve as a reference when designing sustainable wound care packaging. [6]

The EU Green Claims Directive (GCD) could act as a complementary framework to the Medical Device Regulation (MDR) and Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation (PPWR) to substantiate voluntary claims with clear, scientifically-backed evidence by an independent, accredited third-party.

The European Committee for Standardization (CEN) develops technical standards that primarily concern packaging materials. For example, EN 13432 defines requirements for packaging recoverable through composting and biodegradation. [7]

Table 1. Selected CEN standards related to ANIPH BBpPs and packaging.

Standard	Focus	Relevance for ANIPH
EN 13432 (2000)	Compostability and biodegradability of packaging	Ensures claims about compostable packaging are verifiable; relevant for disposal of wound care packaging in contexts with composting options. It is the most common standard.
EN 14995 (2006)	Compostability of non-packaging plastics	Extends compostability testing beyond packaging; relevant for product components or accessories in BBpPs.
EN 15593 (2008)	Hygiene management in packaging production	Ensures sterile packaging production; transferable to medical packaging safety.
EN 17033 (2018)	Biodegradable plastics in soil (mulch films)	Provides test methods and biodegradation benchmarks; useful for assessing degradation under uncontrolled disposal conditions.
EN 13427 (2004) and related standards	Packaging and environment (prevention, reuse, recycling, recovery)	Framework for sustainable packaging design; aligns with EU waste directives, relevant for policy and procurement of BBpPs.

Comment: For biobased carbon content, the most relevant standard, based on the radiocarbon method, is **ASTM D6866** "Standard Test Methods for Determining the Biobased Content of Solid, Liquid, and Gaseous Samples Using Radiocarbon Analysis".

2.2.2. International standards and certifications

At the international level, several standardisation organisations define requirements relevant to information and labelling of biobased and biodegradable plastic products (BBpPs). These include the International Organization for Standardization (ISO), the American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM International), and the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). Each provides methods and frameworks that support comparability of data, certification schemes, and product claims.

ISO Standards

- Medical products: ISO 15223-1 [8] specifies symbols to be used on medical device labels, packaging, and information supplied, to create global consistency in safety and use instructions. ISO 11607-1 and ISO 11607-2 [9] cover requirements for packaging of terminally sterilized medical devices, including design, materials, and validation of sterile barriers.
- Packaging and environmental aspects: ISO 17088 [10] specifies procedures and requirements for compostable plastics, while ISO 14855-1 and ISO 14855-2 [11] define methods for determining ultimate aerobic biodegradability of plastics under controlled composting conditions. ISO 14021 [12] covers environmental labels and self-declared claims, such as “compostable” or “biodegradable,” and provides guidelines to avoid misleading statements.

ASTM Standards

ASTM is another body which creates American standards. Sometimes the ASTM standards are also internationally recognized and adopted.

- ASTM D6400 [13] defines requirements for labelling plastics as compostable in municipal or industrial facilities.
- ASTM D5338 [14] provides a test method for determining aerobic biodegradation of plastic materials under controlled composting conditions.
- ASTM D6954 [15] outlines a standard guide for exposing and testing plastics that degrade in the environment by a combination of oxidation and biodegradation.

US FDA

- Humanitarian Device Exception [16]: Label must state that federal approval is only indicative of device/product’s humanitarian use, not its effectiveness.

OECD Guidelines

OECD test guidelines are primarily designed for chemical testing but are widely used in the context of BBpPs. Of particular relevance are biodegradation tests such as OECD 301 (ready biodegradability) and OECD 302 (inherent biodegradability) [17]. These guidelines are often referenced by certification bodies as they provide internationally recognized methods for assessing environmental fate.

International standards provide a system of methods and requirements that complement European frameworks. For medical wound care packaging, ISO standards on symbols and sterile barrier systems are directly applicable to ensure usability and compliance in international humanitarian operations. For environmental aspects, ISO, ASTM, and OECD biodegradation standards provide the basis for claims about compostability or degradability, which must be verified before such claims are communicated in humanitarian contexts.

2.2.3. Certifications Bodies and Labelling Initiatives

A variety of certification bodies and eco-labels exist for BBpPs. These are often operated by independent certification bodies, industry associations, or NGOs. They are widely used on packaging and consumer products, and in some cases extend to medical packaging materials.

Certification Bodies:

- TÜV Austria (OK Compost / OK Biodegradable / OK Compost Home) [18]
 - Certifies compostability under industrial or home conditions.
 - “OK Biodegradable” variants exist for soil, marine, and freshwater environments.
- DIN CERTCO (Germany)
 - Operates certification for compostable plastics based on EN 13432 and related standards.
 - Includes labels for biobased carbon content (measured against C14 analysis). [19]
- BPI Certification (North America) [20]
 - Biodegradable Products Institute certification, based on ASTM standards.
 - Widely used for consumer packaging, recognised in municipal composting facilities.

Voluntary labelling Initiatives:

- EU Ecolabel (voluntary, public scheme) [21]
 - Covers a wide range of products, including packaging, with strict environmental performance criteria.

- USDA Certified Biobased [22]
 - The U.S federal voluntary label indicates that the product has been certified by the US Department of Agriculture (USDA) to contain the percent biobased content as shown on the label.
- Blue Angel (Germany) [23]
 - Environmental label covering paper, plastics, and packaging, focusing on recyclability and reduced environmental impact.

Table 2. Selected International standards related to ANIPH BBpPs and packaging [18-23].

Standard	Focus	Relevance for ANIPH	Requirement / Voluntary
ISO 15223-1:2021	Symbols on medical device labels	Ensures wound care packaging carries globally recognised safety/use symbols.	MDR, FDA Requirement
ISO 11607-1/2:2019	Packaging for sterilised medical devices	Defines sterile barrier system requirements; critical for medical packaging.	MDR, FDA Requirement
ISO 17088:2021	Specifications for compostable plastics	Provides baseline for claims on compostability of packaging materials.	EU (PPWR) requirement ensure proper EoL management
ISO 14855-1/2	Biodegradability in composting	Standard test methods; relevant for validating ANIPH product claims.	Voluntary
ISO 14021:2016	Environmental self-declared claims	Prevents misleading terms (“biodegradable”, “compostable”) in labels.	Voluntary
ASTM D6400-21	Labelling compostable plastics	Widely used outside the EU; relevant for international acceptance of ANIPH packaging.	Supporting

ASTM D5338-21	Biodegradation test method	Aligns with ISO biodegradation methods; comparability check required.	Supporting
ASTM D6954-18	Plastics degrading by oxidation + biodegradation	Covers materials exposed to open environments; relevant for uncontrolled disposal.	Supporting
OECD 301/302	Ready and inherent biodegradability	Referenced in many eco-labels; useful benchmarks for ANIPH end-of-life pathways.	Supporting

Other notable labels include ÖKOTEX [\[24\]](#) and EMAS [\[25\]](#). These are broader and hence not detailed further.

2.3. Sector-specific ILSs (medical, humanitarian, packaging)

There are sector-specific frameworks that guide information and labelling practices in health and humanitarian contexts. These are crucial for ANIPH, since wound care products and their packaging must meet medical safety requirements while also being usable in low-resource emergency environments.

Medical Device Labelling

- EU Medical Device Regulation (MDR 2017/745) [\[1\]](#) requires labelling of all medical devices with:
 - Safety and risk information.
 - Traceability codes (UDI – Unique Device Identifier).
 - Clear instructions for professional and non-professional users.

- ISO 15223-1 and ISO 20417 provide globally harmonised symbols and requirements for medical device information, ensuring labels are recognisable across regions. [8]

Humanitarian Procurement Frameworks

- WHO and UNICEF procurement guidelines specify product information requirements for wound care products and infection prevention materials. [26]
- UNHCR and Médecins Sans Frontières (MSF) logistics standards include instructions on packaging, labelling, and shelf-life communication for medical supplies in emergencies. [27]
- Emphasis is placed on:
 - Rapid identification of product type and expiry.
 - Durability of labels under extreme conditions (heat, humidity, transport).
 - Multilingual or symbol-based instructions for diverse user groups.

Packaging Initiatives in Healthcare

- **Sterility and hygiene:** Packaging must maintain barrier properties and be labelled with sterilisation method, expiry, and handling precautions (ISO 11607). [9]
- **Waste management guidance:** Labels increasingly include instructions for segregation. [28]

3. Overview of topics concerned with current ILS

Current ILS address a range of dimensions. They include environmental, social, economic, and technical aspects. Their practical value depends on local context.

3.1. Environmental Dimensions

ILS places strong emphasis on environmental performance, particularly for biobased and biodegradable plastics. Standards and certifications cover:

- Biodegradability and compostability under controlled conditions.
- Recyclability and recycling material codes.
- Life-cycle indicators such as biobased origin.
- End-of-life pathways, aligned with available infrastructure.

Table 3. Environmental aspects in current ILS

Aspect	Typical ILS standard or requirement	Example certifier or label	Relevance for ANIPH
Biodegradability and compostability	EN 13432, ISO 17088, ASTM D6400, FTC Green Guides (US)	DIN CERTCO, BPI, OK Compost	Key for wound care packaging claims; must be validated under realistic disposal conditions. Relevant in case industrial or home composting facilities exist; limited applicability in humanitarian settings.
Recyclability	PPWR	Blue Angel, recycling codes	Useful in regions with established collection/recycling; less practical in emergency contexts without infrastructure.
Carbon content	Biobased content certification	DIN CERTCO	Supports SSbD and transparency; relevant for reporting and procurement.

3.2. Social Dimensions

Social aspects receive less attention in current ILS, but some frameworks address usability and accessibility.

Table 4. Social aspects in current ILS

Aspect	Typical ILS Coverage	Relevance for ANIPH
Symbol use	ISO 15223-1, CE Mark (in MDR) [29]	Essential for multilingual humanitarian contexts, CE mark is often used in international procurement too.
Acceptability	WHO/UNICEF procurement, EU ESPR (Digital Product Passport)	Ensures trust and adoption by field workers and end-users. For visibility and integrity of product information

3.3. Economic Dimensions

Economic dimensions are embedded in procurement frameworks or eco-label criteria rather than standalone standards.

- Procurement requirements: Standards and certifications are often mandatory in tenders.
- Market influence: Labels influence buyer decisions and credibility.

Table 5. Economic aspects in current ILS

Aspect	Typical ILS Coverage	Relevance for ANIPH
Procurement criteria	WHO PQ/UNICEF specs, EU tenders	Determine eligibility for humanitarian supply chains.
Market influence	EU Ecolabel, Blue Angel, MDR CE Mark, ESPR Digital Product Passport (DPP), EU Green Claims Directive	Boosts credibility and supports wider adoption.
Claims Substantiation	EU Green Claims Directive, FTC Green Guides (US)	Provides evidence of device feature/property claims

3.4. Technical Dimensions

Technical requirements form the most developed part of current ILS, especially for medical devices and packaging.

- Safety and sterility: Core requirement in medical frameworks.
- Toxicology and material testing: Addressed through OECD and ISO standards.
- Performance validation: Includes barrier properties, shelf life, and usability.
- Traceability: Unique identifiers and coding systems for medical supply chains.

Table 6. Technical aspects in current ILS.

Aspect	Typical ILS Coverage	Relevance for ANIPH
Safety & sterility	MDR, ISO 11607	Critical for wound care packaging.
Toxicology	OECD, ISO, REACH	Needed for Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design evaluation.
Performance	ASTM, EN ISO packaging tests	Ensures products function reliably under stress conditions.
Traceability	MDR UDI	Supports accountability and logistics in humanitarian operations.
Aspect	Typical ILS Coverage	Relevance for ANIPH
Safety & sterility	MDR, ISO 11607	Critical for wound care packaging.
Toxicology	OECD, ISO, REACH	Needed for Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design evaluation.
Performance	ASTM, EN ISO packaging tests	Ensures products function reliably under stress conditions.
Traceability	MDR UDI	Supports accountability and logistics in humanitarian operations.

4. ILS gap analysis

4.1. Overview of gaps that form adoption barriers

Despite many existing information and labelling systems, important gaps remain that limit their effectiveness for biobased and biodegradable plastic products in medical and humanitarian contexts. These gaps occur at: technical validation of materials and additives, environmental assessment of life-cycle and disposal, and socio-economic factors influencing adoption and correct use. Addressing these gaps is important for ANIPH to ensure that wound dressing and their packaging can be reliably assessed and labelled under real-world conditions.

On the technical side, current ILS are not yet adapted to the properties of newer biopolymers such as PHA. Methods for biodegradation testing are often restricted to controlled environments and fail to capture variability in real conditions. Additives introduce further uncertainty, as their toxicity and interactions with biodegradation remain poorly integrated into existing standards. These gaps undermine the credibility of safety and performance claims for BBpPs.

From an environmental perspective, harmonised life-cycle data for medical applications is scarce, and disposal pathways common in humanitarian contexts (open burning, uncontrolled dumping) are rarely reflected in standards. This disconnect reduces the practical value of existing compostability and recyclability labels. At the socio-economic level, barriers include low awareness of BBpPs among buyers, procurement systems that overlook sustainability criteria, and limited adaptation of labels for users with low literacy. Professionals also receive little guidance on how to handle or dispose of sustainable packaging. Together, these issues constrain adoption and may erode trust in BBpPs if not addressed.

Table 7. Overview of identified gaps in current ILS

Category	Aspect	Identified Gaps	Relevance for ANIPH
Technical	PHA materials	Limited standardisation of test methods for biodegradation under variable conditions	Creates uncertainty in claims for wound care and its packaging.
Technical	Additives	Incomplete data on toxicity and biodegradation interaction	Limits ability to apply SSbD criteria.

Technical	Biodegradation testing	Focus on controlled environments (industrial composting) rather than real-world conditions	Not aligned with humanitarian disposal practices.
Environmental	Life-cycle data	Lack of harmonised LCA for BBpPs in medical uses	Difficult to benchmark environmental performance.
Environmental	Disposal pathways	Poor integration of end-of-life realities (open dumping, burning)	Misalignment with actual humanitarian practices.
Environmental	Impact assessment	Limited coverage of secondary impacts (microplastics, emissions from burning)	Reduces credibility of environmental claims.
Socio-economic	Market adoption	Low awareness of BBpPs among healthcare buyers	Limits uptake despite environmental benefits.
Socio-economic	Procurement	Few frameworks include sustainability criteria	Barriers to entry in humanitarian supply systems.
Socio-economic	Cost transparency	Lack of cost-performance benchmarks for BBpPs	Makes comparison with conventional plastics difficult.
Socio-economic	Consumer understanding	Confusion about “biodegradable” vs “compostable”	Leads to incorrect disposal behaviour.
Socio-economic	Professional training	Limited guidance for health workers on sustainable packaging use/disposal	Reduces effective adoption in practice.
Socio-economic	Inclusivity	No adaptation of labels for low-literacy populations	Critical gap in humanitarian settings.

Systemic barriers cut across all three dimensions. These include the persistence of misleading or inconsistent claims, lack of transparency in certification schemes, variation between regional systems (EU, ISO, ASTM), and a poor fit with actual waste management infrastructure in humanitarian settings. These systemic issues highlight why ANIPH needs a tailored approach: one that integrates robust technical data, realistic environmental scenarios, and socio-economic usability into a consistent ILS framework.

5. ILS components relevant for ANIPH products and specification of data points

For ANIPH wound care products and their packaging to be safe, sustainable, and usable in humanitarian contexts, the information and labelling system (ILS) must be built on clearly defined data points. These data points act as the bridge between technical validation and user-facing information. They ensure that sustainability and safety claims are not only verifiable but also usable by healthcare workers, humanitarian responders, and end-users. The following sections identify which components are most relevant for ANIPH and specify the data that needs to be captured.

5.1. Key Data Requirements for ANIPH Materials and Products

The core data categories required for wound care products and their packaging in ANIPH are defined across four dimensions: safety, performance, environmental behaviour, and usability. These categories establish the baseline for an ILS that integrates technical compliance with sustainability and practical application in humanitarian contexts.

Table 8. Key data requirements for ANIPH materials and products

Aspect	Examples of Data Points	Relevance for ILS
Safety	Toxicity of additives, biocompatibility, sterility validation	Ensures MDR compliance and safe-use labelling.
Performance	Barrier properties, shelf life, resistance to heat/humidity	Supports claims about reliability in emergencies.
Environmental	Biodegradation rates, compostability, recyclability, carbon content	Enables credible sustainability claims.
Usability	Clarity of instructions, accessibility (symbols, languages), handling in crisis	Ensures information is actionable in humanitarian contexts.

5.2. Priority SSbD Indicators for ILS Alignment

Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) is the guiding principle for product development in ANIPH. Indicators need to reflect not only compliance with regulatory standards but also alignment with broader sustainability goals. Four clusters of indicators are particularly relevant.

Table 9. Priority SSbD indicators relevant for ANIPH.

Indicator	Measurement / Data Source	Relevance for ANIPH ILS
Human health	Toxicological tests (OECD/ISO)	Mandatory for safety-related labelling.
Environmental safety	Biodegradation tests (ISO 17088, OECD 301/302)	Supports disposal instructions.
Circularity	Carbon content, recyclability codes	Transparent reporting of resource origin.
Societal value	User acceptance studies, procurement guidelines	Ensures adoption in humanitarian settings.

5.3. Technical Specifications for Feedstocks and Additives

Feedstocks and additives determine the fundamental safety and environmental behaviour of ANIPH packaging. Data from these components must be translated into measurable specifications that feed directly into ILS. This ensures that claims about biodegradability, safety, or recyclability are supported by verifiable properties.

Table 10. Technical specifications for feedstocks and additives

Aspect	Data Points	Relevance for ILS
Feedstock origin	Biobased (carbon) content (%), source type, Chemical safety (REACH) [30]	Supports environmental and procurement claims.
Material properties	Mechanical strength, barrier function	Translated into performance labels.
Additives	Type, toxicity, biodegradation impact	Required for SSbD compliance and safe-use instructions.
Variability	Batch consistency, pre-treatment data	Ensures reliable product performance and standardised claims.

6. Strategy to further obtain relevant data/information in other WPs

The mapping of current ILS highlights that not all relevant data for ANIPH wound dressings and its packaging can be extracted from existing systems. Some aspects require new data generation through other Work Packages. The strategy ensures that these data flows are robust, comparable with existing standards, and directly usable for labelling going forward. The data gathering focuses on ingredients and materials used, products, and finally end-of-life systems.

6.1. WP4 and WP5 – Safety and Performance of Materials

The data requirement from WP4: ‘preliminary manufacturing and biodegradation/properties predictive assessment at material level (adhesives, coatings, additives)’ and WP5: ‘safety assessment at material level’ focuses on validation of input ingredients and materials for products and packaging.

- Safety testing (toxicity, biocompatibility).
- Performance validation (barrier properties, shelf life, resilience in variable conditions).
- Data needed for technical sections of ILS (safety, traceability).

Table 11. Data contribution from WP4 and WP5

Aspect	Data Generated	Relevance for ILS
Safety	Microbiological safety, sterilization and validation (MDR CE Mark, FDA Clearance)	Mandatory MDR compliance and label claims.
Toxicology	Leaching, cytotoxicity, additive toxicity (MDR CE Mark, FDA Clearance)	Informs SSbD evaluation and safe use instructions.
Performance	Shelf life, barrier function, stability under stress (MDR CE Mark, FDA Clearance)	Supports labelling for usability in humanitarian supply chains.

Traceability

Unique Device Identifier (UDI) coding Enables global recognition and integration (MDR CE Mark, FDA Clearance) logistics tracking.

6.2. WP8 and WP11 – Safety and Performance of Products

The data requirement from WP8: ‘small scale manufacturing of ANIPH products and biodegradation/properties predictive assessment at product level (wound dressing + packaging)’ and WP11: ‘safe and sustainable end-of-life and safety assessment at product level’ focuses on validation of wound dressing product and packaging characteristics and performance under real-world humanitarian and healthcare conditions.

- Usability and acceptability by health workers and end-users.
- Performance under emergency conditions (heat, humidity, transport stress).

Table 12. Data contribution from WP8 and WP11

Aspect	Data Generated	Relevance for ILS
Usability	User feedback on clarity of labels, handling	Adapt labelling for low-literacy or stressed environments.
Acceptability	Perception by health workers, patients	Guides trust and adoption of labelled claims.
Field performance	Function under transport, climate, storage	Ensures instructions reflect actual conditions of use.

6.3. WP9 – Safety and Performance of the End-of-life System

The data requirement from WP9: ‘end-of-life assessment (biodegradation and recyclability validation) in lab, simulated and real conditions’ focuses on safety and performance of the end-of-life system.

- Disposal pathways and actual end-of-life behaviours.

Table 13. Data contribution from WP9

Aspect	Data Generated	Relevance for ILS
End-of-life	Observation of disposal practices	Provides evidence for realistic waste-related labelling.

7. ILSs from the Consumer Perspective

ILSs are frameworks that help consumers choose, use, and dispose of products, including more (or less) sustainable products [31], [32]. The Circular Economy Action Plan highlights the need to ensure that a product labelled as 'biodegradable' does not mislead consumers and lead them to dispose of it in a manner that causes plastic littering or pollution due to unsuitable environmental conditions or insufficient degradation time [2]. As such, ANIPH aims to address the lack of sufficiently developed or tailored ILSs for BBpPs to favour their adoption and inform consumers. The present chapter aims to review the literature concerning consumer awareness and understanding, perception and attitudes, and behaviour as well as communication needs related to ILSs in the specific context of sustainable health-related packaging. It aims to inform an approach that fosters social acceptability of BBpPs by consumers, including health care professionals, social care professionals, and citizens. It covers literature from 1981 to 2025. Sources were selected from academic databases (i.e., Scopus, Web of Science, PubMed) and institutional reports (i.e., European Commission, OECD). Complementary grey literature (e.g., industry white papers, etc.) was also included to capture emerging trends and applied perspectives.

7.1. Consumer awareness & understanding of ILSs

The current lack of standardisation of ILSs for sustainable products contributes to consumer confusion [33], [34]. This is reflected in a European survey that found that while 71% of respondents expressed a desire to purchase more sustainable products, the majority of them were unable to correctly identify which packaging options were more environmentally friendly [35]. In the context of the food industry, an analysis of the German retail food market demonstrated how most of a set of 14 labels and claims about the sustainability of products were not accurate, transparent, or comprehensible [36]. These sustainability claims were substantiated by a puzzling variety of data sources and methodologies displayed on products. This lack of accuracy, transparency, and comprehensibility adds to consumers' difficulty in understanding environmental attributes such as recyclability or biodegradability. In the context of health care, even if consumers prefer bio-based plastic medical devices over conventional medical devices, many of them have incorrect associations with bio-based plastic products (e.g., only 55.3% of all participants in a survey selected 'Made from biomass') [37]. In medical packaging, ILSs must adhere to strict regulatory requirements (e.g., Regulation (EU) 2017/745 on medical devices [1]) in addition to being

understandable to consumers – health professionals, social care professionals and non-professional users alike – who may have little time and cognitive resources to read and interpret ILSs.

In the context of medical products, a lack of understanding can have more serious consequences, especially for non-professional users [38], [39]. Home users are often elderly or informal caregivers who may struggle with interpreting technical instructions or graphics on labels. Generally, users with adequate literacy levels do not do well when interpreting auxiliary labels: only 37% were found to give correct interpretations [39]. A study aiming to develop easy-to-understand prescription auxiliary labels assessed existing labels and concluded that they were also hard to comprehend for adults with low literacy: less than 50% ‘excellent’ interpretations were given for the labels, except for two of them [40]. For the new labels the authors designed, the use of graphics, increased font size, and coloured background most improved understanding. The authors recommended not to use text that exceeds a sixth-grade level to meet the needs of consumers with low literacy. Indeed, accessibility is a recurrent concern that should be taken into consideration when designing ILSs that support consumers in making informed choices. Elderly users and users with disabilities often face barriers in interpreting packaging despite regulatory efforts, highlighting the need for ILSs that are tailored to real-life cognitive and visual capacities of different user groups [41]. The integration of virtual smart labelling and QR codes that redirect to audio descriptions and other mobile-supported features is helpful, especially when combined with a human-centred design approach [42], [43].

7.2. Consumer perception & attitudes towards ILSs

ILSs do more than conveying information to users. They influence how consumers think about their choices and evaluate products, in turn impacting the market [32], [44]. Labels can highlight values like protecting the environment, shaping consumer perception and attitudes [45]. Even when pursuing similar values, ILSs may differ in standards and the resonance they achieve among their target consumers. They can vary in how strict they are, what values they focus on, and how much trust people have in them [32], [46]. As such, a label is only useful if people believe it is trustworthy. That trust depends on who is responsible for the certification, how effectively it is disseminated to society, how clear standards are, and how carefully products are inspected.

There is growing interest in sustainability issues among consumers, with positive consequences on the perception of and attitudes towards eco-labels [47]. For instance, a large-scale field experiment in fashion e-commerce found that eco-labels can have a positive effect on consumer purchases [48]. Consumers seemed to perceive those labels as a positive extrinsic cue. Nonetheless, some labelling factors impact willingness to pay for some non-medical products. First, a meta-analysis demonstrated that participants in 35 discrete choice experiments reported a willingness to pay

more for foods with an eco-label, especially when a product had an organic label compared with other more specific environmental sustainability labels [49]. This might be because organic labels have a much longer history compared with other environmental sustainability labels, increasing consumer trust and familiarity with organic labels. This shows that the perceived legitimacy of the institution behind the label can impact consumer perception and attitude. Claims supported by public authorities, standardised certification schemes, or reputable associations are perceived as more trustworthy [50]. Unclear affiliations or marketing-driven icons tend to cause scepticism. Without standardised ILSs, consumers must learn or interpret new icons with each product [33], [34]. Detailed, transparent labelling strengthens consumers' perceptions of product safety and brand responsibility, particularly in food and health care contexts [51]. To this effect, standardisation at the EU level has been called for by industry and consumer organisations alike to foster consistency and ease of use [52]. Second, this meta-analysis also found that a combination of text and logo was linked with higher willingness to pay than those employing one or the other. Third, a discrete choice experiment found that participants showed higher willingness to pay for products that employed multi-level labels, hinting at a preference for colourful multi-levels labels and their perceived benefits over binary black-and-white design [51]. Nevertheless, there is a caveat to this finding: participants also preferred products with a multi-level label that were negatively evaluated over products with no label, hinting at a limited effectiveness of eco-labels. Consumers may perceive colourful multi-level labels as better even when they reflect a negative health or environmental evaluation. Finally, the use of multiple labels can backfire as demonstrated by market research into extra-virgin olive oil using a discrete choice experiment [53]. It found that, while the use of two labels had a positive interaction effect, the use of three labels led to label exhaustion, impairing consumer understanding, diminishing the perceived value of verified attributes, and in turn decreasing willingness to pay.

In the context of medical products, including wound dressings, packaging and ILSs have the potential to shape attitudes towards product safety and sustainability as interfaces between the producer and the consumer [43]. There are several factors that can influence consumer perception and attitudes of sustainable medical products. First, packaging that integrates labels with inclusive design elements (i.e., design of products that are accessible to and usable by as many people as possible without special adaptation or specialised design [54]) such as large fonts, tactile cues, colour coding, and audio-readable QR codes tends to be more widely accepted across diverse user groups [42]. This is particularly relevant for elderly users, users with visual impairments, and users with low literacy. Ease of manipulation (i.e., opening, resealing, etc.) also contributes to the perception of the packaging as helpful rather than obstructive. Then, ambiguity and inconsistency between messages communicated on labels of BBpPs, such as when they indicate recyclability

despite the material not being accepted in local waste streams, or when a product has an outer compostable layer but a non-recyclable sterile inner pouch [33] can lead to scepticism over BBpPs. Efforts should be made to improve the clarity and reliability of communications to consumers regarding the source of the material, how the waste is processed, and how to dispose of the material [33], [55]. Ideally, those communications would also include information about availability of alternatives and their implications (e.g., fossil plastic products; eco-labels may be more effective when they are contrasted against negative labels for products that are environmentally harmful [56]) to promote informed decisions, and targeted information about local waste management systems so that consumers know how to dispose of the product and are not left with the impression that biodegradability equates license to litter in the open environment when proper waste management is available.

7.3. Consumer behaviour towards ILSs

Despite growing attitudinal support for sustainable consumption, sustainable behavioural change among consumers remains limited [57]. A persistent challenge in sustainable consumption is the gap between expressed intention and behaviour. For example, while over 70% of consumers reported preferring sustainable packaging options, this does not consistently affect their purchasing patterns [35]. The behavioural reasoning theory helps explain this gap, showing that even positive attitudes towards sustainability must overcome competing reasons against sustainable behaviour (e.g., cost, habit, perceived risk, etc.) to influence intention and innovation adoption [58]. According to this theory, behaviour is shaped by intention which is shaped by beliefs and values, reasons for and against the behaviour, and motives (i.e., attitude, subjective norm, perceived control). This section investigates key barriers and enablers to translating consumer attitudes into action.

In health care, consumers may agree that eco-friendly products are preferable yet still choose cheaper or more familiar options, particularly under time pressure or when dealing with medical uncertainty [33], [34]. Importantly, purchasing decisions are not only made by health care professionals or end users: medical providers and health care centres significantly shape the availability, affordability, and perceived legitimacy of products, thereby influencing how end users interact with, and trust medical devices [59]. Uncertainty of ILSs is a primary barrier for behavioural change. If consumers struggle to interpret terms like “compostable” or “biocompatible,” their likelihood of using the information in decision-making drops. In health-related packaging, this becomes even more salient due to the stressful context of use (e.g., emergency wound dressing changes). Labels that provide concise, well-positioned information [43] and avoid technical jargon are more likely to lead to behaviour change [60]. Moreover, the presence of many labels can lead

to a sense of saturation resulting in selective inattention where important safety or disposal instructions are ignored. Cognitive load increases with each additional claim, especially under time pressure.

Many factors can shift behaviour to be more sustainable. First, social influence has an impactful effect on behaviour as consumers are influenced by the presence, expectations, and behaviours of social others [57]. For instance, through social identities, consumers can be encouraged to engage in sustainable actions if other in-group members (e.g., neighbours, colleagues, etc.) also perform them [61], [62]. Interventions based on peer influence or social proof such as caregiver testimonials linked to ILSs can increase uptake of sustainable choices. Second, habit is another critical component of sustainable behaviour change: many common habits like resource use and disposal of products are strongly habitual [57]. Since breaking habits is viewed as effortful, making an action easier to do is a good strategy to encourage sustainable habit formation [63]. Requiring less sorting of recyclables and placing recyclable bins in an accessible and visible space in health care environments would be useful contextual cues for increasing sustainable habit formation in addition to clear disposal instructions in ILSs [64]. Finally, tangibility is another useful component [57]: communications that relate to more proximal consequences of sustainable behaviours for a given neighbourhood, city, or region can make action and outcomes seem more tangible and relevant (e.g., highlighting current issues like extreme weather [65] [66]).

7.4. Communication Needs for ILSs

This last section aims to provide actionable recommendations to design ILSs so that they positively impact consumer awareness and understanding, consumer perception and attitudes, and consumer behaviour.

First, to increase consumer awareness and understanding across consumer groups of different abilities, ILSs should:

- Include accurate, transparent, and comprehensible sustainability claims, claims for a product class should be substantiated by the same data sources and methodologies.
- Establish correct associations with bio-based plastic medical devices (e.g., ‘made from biomass’).
- Use graphics, increased font size, and coloured background in addition to avoiding text that surpasses a sixth grade reading level.
- Integrate virtual smart labelling and QR codes that redirect to audio descriptions and other mobile-supported features.

- Elaborate on the absence of persistent micro- and nanoplastics when biobased and biodegradable alternatives and substitutes like PHA are used, particularly in the critical context of healthcare.

Second, to improve consumer perception and attitudes, ILSs should:

- Use a simple, standardised certification scheme with institutional backing to boost consumer trust and familiarity and prevent them having to relearn new ILSs for different products.
- Include a logo along with text.
- Avoid the use of more than two labels to avoid label exhaustion that diminishes the perceived value of verified attributes.
- Be combined with packaging that follows inclusive design principles
- Provide clear and reliable information regarding the source of the material, how the waste is processed, and how to dispose of the material, as well as information about availability of alternatives to promote informed decisions.
- Provide localised information about waste management systems so that consumers know how to dispose of the product.

Lastly, to bridge the gap between consumer intention and behaviour, ILSs should:

- Be supported by dissemination strategies to medical providers and health care centres as the latter can influence availability, affordability, and perceived legitimacy of BBpPs.
- Provide concise, well-positioned, and direct instructions that enable appropriate behaviour and avoid technical jargon and excessive use of labels to prevent instructions from being ignored.
- Capitalise on social influence by having professional consumers influence other professional and non-professional consumers around them to engage in more sustainable behaviour.
- Facilitate new habit formation by being combined with waste management systems that require less sorting of recyclables and that provide the appropriate bins placed in visible locations in health care environments.
- Capitalise on tangibility by relating to BBpPs' sustainability in terms of minimisation of adverse proximal environmental consequences.

8. Conclusion

The mapping of information and labelling systems (ILS) shows that a wide range of standards, certification schemes, and eco-labels already exist at European and international levels. These provide a useful foundation for assessing biobased and biodegradable plastic products (BBpPs), including wound care packaging. However, the review also reveals limitations. Current ILSs are largely oriented towards conventional consumer packaging or controlled industrial contexts and do not fully address the specific requirements of medical devices or the realities of humanitarian settings.

Three main areas of gaps have been identified. On the technical side, there is insufficient standardisation for PHA materials and their additives, and existing biodegradation tests focus on industrial conditions rather than open or low-infrastructure environments. On the environmental side, gaps remain in harmonised life-cycle data and in accounting for realistic end-of-life pathways such as open dumping or burning, which are common in crisis situations. The socio-economic dimension is underrepresented, with limited integration of procurement criteria, low awareness of BBpPs among buyers, and insufficient attention to accessibility and comprehensibility of labels for diverse user groups. These gaps are reinforced by systemic issues such as inconsistent claims across regions, lack of transparency in certification, and poor alignment with local waste management infrastructure.

For the ANIPH project, these findings highlight the need for a tailored ILS framework that integrates Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) indicators, technical specifications, environmental performance, and user-centred communication. The outputs of this mapping exercise provide the baseline for subsequent work packages. WP4 will generate robust safety and performance data, WP9 will validate usability and end-of-life aspects in real humanitarian contexts, and WP11 will support the translation of results into standardisation and policy.

This deliverable therefore plays a bridging role. It establishes the reference point for evaluating BBpPs against existing ILS, identifies where new evidence is required, and frames the design of a system that can communicate safety, sustainability, and usability in an integrated way. The outcomes will directly feed into D11.5 (Final ANIPH contributions to ILSs), which will consolidate the project's recommendations for standardisation and labelling frameworks, and D12.1 (Final report on policy briefs/recommendations), which will translate these findings into policy-oriented

guidance. Together, these contributions will support the development and adoption of safe and sustainable wound care products and packaging solutions for humanitarian contexts, reinforcing both environmental responsibility and societal value.

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